

THE TYPOLOGY OF LEGENDS ABOUT HISTORICAL FIGURES IN KARAKALPAK AND ENGLISH FOLKLORE

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Abstract: Legends, which include part of the folklore heritage, are one of the main genres of oral creativity of the Turkic peoples. In the world science of folklore and literary criticism, a large number of works have been published on the definition of theoretical descriptions of legends. In this article we tried to describe one of the epic genres of folk oral tradition, historical legends, their characteristic features, images, historical figures and plot issues on the example Karakalpak and English folklore materials. The issues of their typology are also determined.

Key words: image, historical figure, historical story, plot, genre, hero, motive, episode, typology, Ernazar Alakoz, King Arthur. In the world of folklore studies, theoretical concepts developed by mythological, historical, anthropological, ritual-mythological, schools of the theory of "nomadic plots" on the genesis and classification of epic genres such as myth, legend, legend, fairy tale, their comparative-historical, comparative-typological and others pointed out that the systematic collection of materials characteristic of folk tales and their preparation for publication, as well as the problems of learning them, are of great importance. Therefore, the genre characteristics of legends, similarities and differences of folk prose from epic genres like legends, fairy tales, proverbs, epics, etc., the description of real life events in the plot, creation of poetic composition, creation of motifs, system of images, method of narration, clarity of issues related to language are one of the topical issues facing today's folklore studies and enriching them from the theoretical point of view is of great importance. Therefore, in this article, we will try to compare the problems of real images in legends, legends about historical figures, using the example of Karakalpak and English folklore.

One of the most common images in the historical legends of the world and Turkish folklore is the image of historical figures. In the plot of the legend, historical figures appear as protagonists or episodic characters and perform their own artistic function. In historical narratives, the image of a historical figure is portrayed as a brave, manly, hardworking, wise person who protects the people, and by highlighting the humane qualities of the historical figure and

artistically portraying his activities for the people, the historical figure rises to the level of an ideal hero. Therefore, people manage to create prototype images of historical figures. "One of the main features of the genre of legend is the delivery of the story, which is related to epic narratives. In legends, the plot orientation plays the role of an introductory plot, connecting the events with each other. A certain event related to the hero's marriage and business in the work serves to complement the scenes of the situation. It proves the expressed opinion, idealizes the historical figures by enriching the content. The main function of historical legends is to inform about real events. "Legend" genre contains the content of historical information [1; p.7]."

In Turkish folk tales, the image of rulers or military commanders and warriors is explained in a particularly loving and noble spirit. For example, in the folklore of Karakalpak we can see the following legends " A word about Muraly-Sher and Sultan Suyin's ", "Maman Biy's dream", "Maman Biy's descent from Title", "Esengeldi and Aydos Biy", "Aidos Biy", "Ernazar Alakoz - Noker", "Ispandiyar Khan", "Arastu's will to Alexander" and others.

One of the most widespread historical legends in Karakalpak folklore is "Ernazar Alakoz - Servant", in which Ernazar Alakoz is depicted as a folk hero. According to the historical literature, Ernazar Alakoz, the leader of Karakalpaks, led the popular uprising in 1855-56. In the years 1850-55, there were continuous wars in the Khanate of Khiva, famine and infectious diseases (plague, plague) spread. Because the canals were not dug, there were water shortages, and the amount and types of taxes collected from the people increased. Thus, the condition of the peoples of the Khiva Khanate, including the Karakalpaks, reached an unbearable level in this era, and in 1855, it led to the emergence of a popular uprising against Khiva rule [2; pp.218-225].

According to the story of "Ernazar Alakoz - Nöker"[3; p.111], which is a story of such historical events, during one of the wars against the kings of Iran, Khiva Khan was defeated, his servants left him and ran away. Ernazar saw this and gave his own horse taking the Khiva Khan's weak horse. Riding the weak horse Ernazar was captured by two Iranian soldiers, but Ernazar's ingenuity and wisdom saved him, and stories like how he found the soul of the mother of the two soldiers who captured him. The stories of Ernazar Biy and his heroism for the sake of the people, and his civic services, make up the plot of the story. Along with that, it is noticeable that Ernazar Biy has a great organizational skill. In other words, he is doing his best to save the king from his enemies, without fearing even the enemy that comes to him. It is clear from the legend that

Ernazar is a hero with a heart and a brave young man. Therefore, Ernazar Biy is described as an epic hero of historical events. The image of Ernazar in the legend educates people to like freedom and be brave. It can be of great importance in creating the ideas of struggle for freedom, freedom, and human rights in the reader

There are also historical legends of English folklore and historical legends of such historical figures. For example, in English folklore Robin Hood, King Arthur, Guy of Warwick, The Cauld Lad of Hylton, Jack the Giant Killer, Learn More About England's Famous Mythological Figures and others. There are legends about historical figures. Several legends about King Arthur were created in the work of these people. Because King Arthur "If there's one legend that could be said to encapsulate the idea of Britain in ancient times, it has to be the legend of King Arthur. This most famous of British kings was said to have defended the country against Saxon invaders in the 5th and early 6th centuries, and he's been the subject of numerous stories that have achieved mythical status in Britain. Everyone is familiar with the stories of King Arthur, his wife Guinevere and his Knights of the Round Table, in particular Lancelot, who fell in love with Guinevere and rescued her from the resulting threat of execution by Arthur, leading to war between Lancelot and Arthur. The Round Table is a powerful Arthurian symbol; it was given to Arthur by his father-in-law as a dowry, and it was said to be round to avoid squabbles between the knights over who was most important. Among the most famous tales is Arthur's search for the Holy Grail – the cup that contained the blood of Christ (a story satirised in Monty Python and the Holy Grail). The magician Merlin is another key figure in the Arthurian legends; Merlin placed a sword in a stone and whomever was able to pull it out would be king. Only Arthur could do it.

King Arthur has come to represent the battle for good against evil, but the myth and romance surrounding him have little basis in historic fact, and there's been much debate over whether he was really a historical figure. Only vague traces of historical and archaeological evidence exist, and versions of stories differ; he may have been a real person, but the stories are, of course, highly embellished if not pure fiction. However, King Arthur has been enormously influential in British society and culture for centuries. For example, Arthurian lineage provided justification for the power of the Tudor monarchs, and the legends were particularly in vogue during the Victorian period, when they inspired artists and writers. These days, visitors flock to Tintagel Castle in

Cornwall, a dramatic ruin imposingly situated on the rugged Cornish coastline and supposedly the place where King Arthur was conceived”[4].

In the legend, the historical truth that tells about the bravery of King Arthur is reflected in the minds of the people. As a result of this, several legends appeared about the character of King Arthur. In their plot system, some traditional motifs of English folklore are depicted. It can be understood that special value was given to King Arthur's real life activities in such legends,

According to one of these legends, "There's now general acceptance that behind the legendary figure of Arthur stands a real historical personage, a great leader named Arturus, who championed the Celtic Britons' cause against the Anglo-Saxons in the 5th century. However, his name does not appear in any reliable history of the period, probably because Arturus was not his proper name, but a title meaning Bear.

We can also find such information which describes historical events like

This may explain the myriad of places in Britain that claim a connection to the legendary King [5]”seen that King Arthur was a brave, a courageous, and a hardworking man. This characteristic of him is reflected in legends in its own epic style.

In conclusion, when we compare the given materials, we can see the description of heroism and valor historical figures in such legends on the theme of heroism, which tells about the fight against enemies in Karakalpak and English folklore. Moreover, they attract the attention of the reader because they were the people who really existed in history.

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